

One Health EJP, Grand No.773830

JRP9-Air Sample

**Air-sampling: A Low-Cost Screening Tool in Biosecured Broiler
Production**

Data management Plan. V1

March 2019

Data management Plan

AIR SAMPLE , One Health EJP, Grand No.773830

Report V1

2019

By

Julia Christensen

Academic officer,

National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark

Research Group for Microbiology and Hygiene

Copyright: Reproduction of this publication in whole or in part must include the customary bibliographic citation, including author attribution, report title, etc.

Published by: DTU, National Food Institute, Kemitorvet, Building 204, 2800 Kgs. Lyngby
Denmark
www.food.dtu.dk

Table of Contents

Summary	4
1. The Air-sample data Summary	5
2. Restrictions to the data	5
3. Data storage and security	5
4. Documentation	5
4.1 Metadata to be associated with the data	5
4.2 Documentation that will accompany the data	6
5. Data sharing	6
5.1 Data will be shared	6
5.2 Data will be shared for possible reuse	6
6. Long-term preservation	7
7. Allocation of resources	7

Summary

An DMP (D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation WP4 Joint Integrative Projects) defines the strategy on how One Health EJP (OHEJP) data are managed under conditions that conform with the requirements of Horizon 2020. As the OHEJP is a co-funded program, agreements between partners and stakeholders are required to collect/process/use data. It must acknowledged that the source of co-funding may have priority in some decisions regarding data management, i.e. that it may dictate where and how the programme output, including data, should be deposited and named. Consequently, the principles provided by the OHEJP overarching DMP meant to complement any requirements from individual funders, while still ensuring that the data are FAIR, as far as possible.

A data management plan (DMP) is a written document that describes the expected data to acquire or generate during of a research project. It describes how to manage, describe, analyze, and store those data, and what mechanisms will use at the end of project to share and preserve data (D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation WP4 Joint Integrative Projects).

A data management plan, describes the collected or generated data, and what happens to this data during its life cycle (storage, publication, citation, long-term availability, anonymity, deletion, etc.).

The goal of a data management plan is to meet the requirements of good scientific practice and to allow for reproducibility of research results. It is recommended to start early with the preparations for the handling of research data and to update the procedures during the project (D4.7 Guidelines for Data Management Plan implementation WP4 Joint Integrative Projects).

1. The Air-sample data Summary

On-farm sampling of poultry done by taking boot swabs and the air samples on gelatine filters by staff of DTU (Denmark) , NVI (Norway), VRI (Czech Republic), NVRI (Poland) and IZSAM (Italy). Boot swabs and air samples kept at room temperature until analyses. At least to Eppendorf tubes with enriched samples stored at min at -70°C or below.

These samples are analysed qualitatively for the presence of Campylobacter by culture-based method according ISO 10272-1, PCR and metagenomics sequencing and bioinformatics.

The raw data resulting from these analyses are in different file formats (mxp, txt, fastq.qz), , but most can be exported to Microsoft Excel (xls or xlsx).

The estimated amount of data is several hundred GB.

The data structured so that each analysis result can be traced back to the sample it belongs to analyses number and date.

Analyses of raw data stored in FASTA files, Mx 3000P and Mx3005P QPCR Systems instruments storage, Microsoft Excel files, Microsoft Word, PDF, Analyses reports in Institutions servers of project participant countries.

2. Restrictions to the data

This project does not make use of animals and will not impact any societal or ethical aspects.

The identity of farms participating in the sampling plans will not be revealed.

All personal and business data collected will treated confidentially and in accordance with strict national and EU data law.

3. Data storage and security

Raw data and results are stored on Institutions servers of project participants countries drives and backed up with institutions backed up programs.

Data shared with collaboration partners through the One Health European Joint Programme side <https://onehealthejp.eu/groups/air-sample/> ,mails, presentations.

The identity of farms participating in the sampling plans will not be revealed. All personal and business data collected will be treated confidentially and in accordance with strict national and EU data law.

4. Documentation

4.1 Metadata to be associated with the data.

4.1.1 The metadata associated with sample collection includes:

1. Type of farm with biosecurity measures: organic or conventional farm (open housing farms must be excluded). 2. Size of the farm (number of houses). 3. Size of the house (square meters; or length x breadth). 4. Size of flock (number of chicken per house). 5. Type of bedding: Shavings, sawdust, straw, paper, peat, etc. 6. Age of chicken coming in and out the house. 7. Feed composition or feed compound type. 8. Additional equipment (floor heating, fly net, etc.). 9. Type of chicken breed. 10. Chicken supplier. 11. Number of breeding cycles per house and year. 12. Type of disinfection. 13. Biosecurity measures (rodent and insect control, dead-bird disposal, water sanitation, litter removal, visitor's control, owner's pets on the farm). 14. Health care anamnestic data (use of antibiotics; first week mortality). 15. Date. 16. Age of animals (days). 17. Outside temperature. 18. Indoor temperature. 19. Farm region (not exact address, because identity of farms participating in the sampling plans are not revealed).

4.1.2 The metadata associated with analyses:

Result of cultural ISO methods, results of molecular biological methods, results of sequencing and metagenomics analyses, results of bioinformatics, sample bank overview.

4.2 Documentation that will accompany the data.

The aim of this study is to document that the new air sampling method gives a similar performance as ISO-10272-1, in order to achieve the ISO approval of the air sampling method, so data (results) will be associated with analyses electronic journals/ reports in Institutions servers of project participant countries.

The level of statistical agreement of the results between the two methods will be tested in the end of the project.

5. Data sharing

5.1 Data will be shared.

Questionnaire data, methods and results from the different analysis methods will be shared between partners by mail and presentations. Raw data from sequencing and metagenomics analyses, quality controls reports and bioinformatics analyses will be shared between partners by uploading to Norwegian Veterinary Institute.

Data openly accessible will be shared through publication in peer-reviewed journals.

Data also shared with collaboration partners through the One Health European Joint Programme side <https://onehealth.eu/groups/air-sample/>, mails, presentations. The results from the different analysis will be collected in several different files for different methods and from different software deemed relevant. Analysis reports and presentation will be stored in Microsoft Excel files, Microsoft Word, PDF on the department drives in Institutions servers of project participant countries.

The general public will have access to the data through publication in peer-reviewed journals.

5.2 Data will be shared for possible reuse.

- Any potential technology or novel finding will be explored for possible patenting or commercial use.
- Protocols and guidelines will be made available online and submitted to EFSA, ISO, CEN or national authorities involved in food safety.
- Special emphasis will be given to hands-on workshops and involvement of reference laboratories in implementing the final air sampling protocol on One Health European Joint Programme side <https://onehealthjep.eu/groups/air-sample/>
- The Stakeholder Board planned will be actively involved in the dissemination period (Year 2) in order to expand the outreach of the proposal beyond the EJP partners.
- Protocols and methods will be presented as animation and uploaded online to reach end-users, which in this case are reference laboratories, chicken producers, or regulators.
- The scientist involved will publish the outcome in international peer-reviewed journals and, where possible, relevant national journals in own native language.
-

6. Long-term preservation

Institutional repository at National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Norwegian Veterinary Institute, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise Italy. (available from January 2019).

All Danish raw data, analyses and results will also remain with coordinator Jeffrey Hoorfar, professor at DTU Food after the end of the project.

Raw data of other participants will remain with authors of proposal.

7. Allocation of resources

Cost related to open-access to research data in Horizon 2020 are eligible for reimbursement under the conditions defined in the H2020 Grand Agreement. Project has apply for resources and waiting for the answer.